

Needs of pedagogical practices related to recent trends in Teacher Education

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ABSTRACT

With digitalization, privatisation, liberalization and globalization in education, there has been major change in entire ecosystem of the education system. And, to cater these changes, there has been shift in pedagogical practices from traditional teaching to modern teaching methodology. This article discussed the need for changes or updating of pedagogical practices with respect to recent trends in teacher education because of huge technological developments and subsequent change in demands for type of knowledge and skills required in today's world.

Keywords: Pedagogical Practices, Teacher Education and its Recent Trends

INTRODUCTION

Teacher education is continuously evolving past few decades and with the advancement of technology and subsequently, introduction of National Education Policy (NEP 2020), there has been acute need to update pedagogical practices to make learning a joyful experience for the students by making learning child-centric. NEP 2020 aims to promote higher order skills such as creativity, idea generation, problem solving, critical thinking, etc, hence this shift of focus from assessment based on academic grades to higher order skills require updating the pedagogy in accordance with National Curriculum Framework (NCF-2005) and National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (NCFTE-2009) to promote critical learning and change the focus from product-based learning, which is related to mastery by the teacher in the contextual knowledge, which was traditional method of teaching to process-based learning, which focuses on child centric progressive learning. This article will discuss some of the factors that contributed towards new pedagogical changes in accordance with recent trends in teacher education to commit joyful and congenial environment for learners.

KEY FACTORS TRIGGERING DEVELOPMENT OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES

1. Emerging demand for knowledge-based society

With the development of new knowledge, it has become difficult to compress all that knowledge and educate the students in a limited time span. Hence, it became necessary to adopt some pedagogical changes that inculcate students with the ability to analyse, evaluate and apply this knowledge by themselves using critical thinking and self-learning ability, so that they can continue lifelong learning with development of new knowledge.

2. Technological advancements

Technological developments have allowed students to widen their boundaries and gain access to vast amount of knowledge. Developments in the fields of artificial intelligence for teaching and learning, virtual and augmented reality, etc have allowed teachers to increase the motivation and engagement of students towards learning with improved speed. Also, gamification have changed the attitude of learning. It allows students to develop required skills and gain knowledge and even develop critical thinking ability through games and virtual simulations of the real-world scenarios.

So, inclusion of these technologies in pedagogical changes, in accordance with central bodies concerned, is a must in today's education system to cater the demands of the century.

3. Shift towards non-conventional courses

In our country, there has always been a huge demand for courses among students offering career as Engineers, Doctors, Lawyers, Accountants, etc. But, with the advancement of technology and improvement in internet services in India, there has been a steep change in the type, ethics and culture of the work in today's world that resulted in shift of the demand to a greater extent towards skills and vocational courses in areas such as Video Editing, Web Designing, Marketing, Fashion, Public Relations and Communications, Machine Learning, Data Science, Data Analytics and even specialisation in Edu-Tech programs. These skills demand students with ability to critically analyse, learn and apply the knowledge by themselves through self-learning even after graduation (life-long learning). So, pedagogy needed update with respect to above changes in trends.

4. Change in students' expectations

Recent changes in student demographics suggests that students want to combine work and study, hence, they are moving more towards flexible learning options alongside their work. This change in students' expectations is a consequence of various factors such as, advancement in technology that led to change in world of work, that is, shift of preferences towards non-conventional courses and skill development in their respective fields. Also, an ideal student needs to study for several years before finding a way to use that knowledge to earn a living because of emerging pile of new knowledge in today's world. These changes created a demand for pedagogical changes such as using blended or hybrid learning or flipped classroom and etc.

CONTRIBUTORS TOWARDS DEVELOPMENT OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES

1. Blended learning

In hybrid or blended learning, there is integration or blending of traditional classroom with online teaching. In this flipped classroom method, teachers provide students with online resources such as videos, readings, open education resources, online library access, quizzes, etc, which students work on prior to coming to the class. This saves the substantial classroom time and facilitate better utilization of classroom time by promoting interaction between teacher and students through discussions, problem-solving, case studies, practical exercises or lab work. This method of teaching provides flexibility and wide access to resources through internet and etc and experts through face-to-face interaction between teacher and students.

2. Use of Multimedia and Open Educational Resources (OER)

Improved internet services led to accessibility of wide range of digital media resources or OER for free in the form of short lectures, animations, simulations, VR videos, virtual labs and many more. This helped the students to master the key concepts or techniques and relate it with the real-world scenarios and also help them remain focused and motivated during the study hours. Even modern-day text books have incorporated links to video and audio clips or animations to allow for easy understanding and better interaction during learning. OER and multimedia have also played a vital role in catering the changing demands of students by allowing them with flexible study plans along with their work and other skills developments. Integration of course specific OER in the core course content will establish a cost and time effective learning-teaching option for students as well as teachers and with the introduction of e-textbooks, students can widen their boundaries by accessing open-source materials at lower cost via mobile smartphones, tablets, e-readers and other digital devices that will lead to better quality in education in our country.

3. Digital media as a facilitator towards building a class of wider community through collaborative approach

With use of social media, there have been development of groups or communities of interested students and teachers for discussion on theories and real-life challenges and share experiences to learn from others. This practice is often encouraged by teachers as teachers cannot deliver all the knowledge or provide all the sources of learning to the students in a limited time span of classroom interaction, hence, they promote building up of communities of like-minded students, just like a virtual classroom, where teachers maintain a critical role as guide, facilitator and assessor of the learning in that community. This pedagogy of teaching is based on the idea of engaged learning and promotes interaction among students similar to their interaction in physical world on a daily basis, hence, learning experience will be similar to normal conversation with friends and colleagues which will help students retain, analyse and apply the knowledge gained in the real world better by using experiences of others.

4. Increasing Just in time learning demands

Since learning materials can be accessed from anywhere and anytime using various digital devices, so there is increasing demand from students for smaller learning modules that cater an immediate learning need. These just in time learning modules fit the needs of many students who are working part-time and also for those students who are in search for flexibility in learning. These modules have been integrated with full time degrees, diplomas or certification courses by awarding some badges or microcredits on completion of these smaller learning modules. These can be assessed through various digital devices and offer quizzes, multimedia learning resources and connection among students for better understanding and quality skill development among students by facilitating independent learning.

5. New ways of assessment to evaluate performance

NEP 2020 has suggested to restructure the curriculum and pedagogy to focus on higher order skill development such as creativity, idea generation, problem solving, critical-thinking, etc. Hence, to evaluate the performance of students on the basis of these higher order skills, there must be a shift from conventional methods of examination to modern day methods involving technology. Evaluation can be done using peer-review assessments, where students will review each other's work, provide ratings on various parameters and will provide feedbacks to be later used for better understanding of the issues. Teachers can also rate and review their students on similar kinds of parameters related to performance in required skillsets. Also, by collecting, storing and assessing a student's multimedia online activities and his/her contributions to the online discussions and quizzes or etc, e-portfolios can be maintained of students to facilitate evaluation and improvements in required areas in learnings. Through learning analytics, e-portfolios can easily be analysed and evaluated with useful feedbacks from it like diagnosing students' areas of weaknesses, assessing the quality and usefulness of course materials and efficiency of the course material in motivating students for maximizing participation and providing opportunities and etc.

Students can also be evaluated using online test systems backed and powered by AI. AI-based programs offer insights into student's performance and the group of each topic or subject and eliminate the biases that arise during manual evaluation of the test papers.

6. Changes to provide students with more control, choice and Independence

To fulfil the objective of new education policy of 2020 of focussing on higher order skill developments, there is need to design the courses flexible enough in terms of content choice, delivery, assessments to cater multiple needs of different students. This can be done by changing the role of teacher or instructor to that of a facilitator or guide towards guiding the students to access the right type of knowledge relevant to the course content from the vast sea of knowledge available via internet through multiple sources, unlike the traditional method, where teachers strictly manage a set of curriculums with limited content, which has become irrelevant in front of the technological exposure a student has in today's world. So, here students take responsibility of their own learning and will undertake their personalised approach of learning a particular skillset. Also, according to NEP 2020, it is also necessary to focus on the use of mother tongue as the medium of instruction for the courses taught till class 8 so that students grasp the complex concepts easily and can relate it with their everyday life. These all changes have increased students' control over the curriculum and have provided with lots of choices and independence in the education system.

CONCLUSION

Teaching is a complex process owing to uniqueness in the learning ability of different students. So, integration and updating of innovative pedagogical strategies with the emerging changes in the world is of utmost important for efficient, effective and valuable learning. With the advancements in technology, there has been a steep change in the learning methodology and these changes led to three emerging pedagogical trends to enable teaching in modern era effectively:

- a. Shift from classroom being the unique centre of learning and knowledge where information was delivered through lectures, to vast sea of knowledge accessible to all for free via internet that makes up the learning more flexible and provided more control, choice and independence to the learners.
- b. Increased dependency on technology for not only teaching, but also to help teachers evaluate the performance of students and also for students to evaluate themselves and provide assistance and support for identifying the weak areas in either the student's performance or the course structure and to improve it with required measures and changes.
- c. Increased sharing of power between the student and the instructor. This is because of social media, peer-review assessments, discussion groups and even online community study groups where students support each other but with guidance, support and feedback from teachers or instructors. Also, unlike traditional method of developing a set of curriculums with limited content for all students, there shift of focus towards developing more flexible and student-friendly curriculum that focus more towards providing guidance for to gain access to right type of knowledge among multiple sources via internet.

So, discussed above in this article truly justify the fact that need of relevant pedagogical practices with changing world is the core for the development of human civilisation as a good pedagogical tool will enable teachers to cultivate the right and efficient skills and knowledge in the minds of learners, and using these humans will be able to carry forward the journey of developments towards a brighter path.

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